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Double Fractional Integral Inequalities for Co-ordinated Convex Functions

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Abstract

The primary objective of this study is to establish novel Ostrowski-type fractional integral inequalities for functions whose powers of the absolute values of partial derivatives are convex on the coordinates. By utilizing a fractional integral identity previously proposed in the literature, several generalized versions of these inequalities are derived. In addition, various special cases and related corollaries are provided to emphasize the importance and applicability of the obtained results.

Keywords: Fractional integrals, Co-ordinated convex functions, Ostrowski type inequalities, Double integrals.

1. Introduction

The study one of the most fundamental and influential integral inequalities in mathematical analysis is the celebrated Ostrowski inequality, established by Alexander Markovich Ostrowski [16] in 1938. In its classical form, this inequality provides an upper bound for the error between the value of a function at any point $x \in [a, b]$ and its integral average over that interval. This bound is expressed in terms of the maximum norm of the function's first derivative, f' . The significance of this inequality stems from its utility as a powerful tool in various fields, particularly in error analysis for numerical integration and probability theory. The practical significance of the Ostrowski inequality is particularly evident in numerical analysis and the theory of special means. It is extensively applied to estimate the error bounds for various quadrature formulae, including the well-known midpoint, trapezoid, and Simpson rules.

Firstly, we give the definitions of Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals:

Definition 1. [11] Let $f \in L_1[a, b]$. The Riemann-Liouville integrals $J_{a+}^\alpha f$ and $J_{b-}^\alpha f$ of order $\alpha > 0$ with $a \geq 0$ are defined by

$$J_{a+}^\alpha f(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_a^x (x-t)^{\alpha-1} f(t) dt, \quad x > a$$

and

$$J_{b-}^\alpha f(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_x^b (t-x)^{\alpha-1} f(t) dt, \quad x < b$$

respectively. Here, $\Gamma(\alpha)$ is the Gamma function and $J_{a+}^0 f(x) = J_{b-}^0 f(x) = f(x)$.

An essential component of our investigation involves the Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals for functions of two variables, defined as follows.

Definition 2. [19] Let $f \in L_1([a, b] \times [c, d])$. The Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals $J_{a+,c+}^{\alpha,\beta}$, $J_{a+,d-}^{\alpha,\beta}$, $J_{b-,c+}^{\alpha,\beta}$ and $J_{b-,d-}^{\alpha,\beta}$ are defined by

$$J_{a+,c+}^{\alpha,\beta} f(x, y) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)\Gamma(\beta)} \int_a^x \int_c^y (x-t)^{\alpha-1} (y-s)^{\beta-1} f(t, s) ds dt, \quad x > a, y > c,$$

$$J_{a+,d-}^{\alpha,\beta} f(x, y) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)\Gamma(\beta)} \int_a^x \int_y^d (x-t)^{\alpha-1} (s-y)^{\beta-1} f(t, s) ds dt, \quad x > a, y < d,$$

$$J_{b-,c+}^{\alpha,\beta} f(x, y) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)\Gamma(\beta)} \int_x^b \int_c^y (t-x)^{\alpha-1} (y-s)^{\beta-1} f(t, s) ds dt, \quad x < b, y > c,$$

and

$$J_{b-,d-}^{\alpha,\beta} f(x, y) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)\Gamma(\beta)} \int_x^b \int_y^d (t-x)^{\alpha-1} (s-y)^{\beta-1} f(t, s) ds dt, \quad x < b, y < d.$$

Finally, the concept of co-ordinates convex, which will be used in this article, will be mentioned. A formal definition for co-ordinated convex function may be stated as follows:

Definition 3. A function $f: \Delta \rightarrow R$ will be called co-ordinated convex on Δ , for all $t, s \in [0, 1]$ and $(x, y), (u, v) \in \Delta$, if the following inequality holds:

$$\begin{aligned} & f(tx + (1-t)y, su + (1-s)v) \\ & \leq tsf(x, u) + s(1-t)f(y, u) + t(1-s)f(x, v) + (1-t)(1-s)f(y, v). \end{aligned}$$

Clearly, every convex function is co-ordinated convex. Furthermore, there exist co-ordinated convex function which is not convex, (see, [2]).

Following the presentation of the basic definitions and notions utilized throughout this work, the next step is to discuss the main studies in the literature concerning these topics. In the referenced works [3]-[5], Dragomir employed identities involving the sum of the right- and left-sided Riemann-Liouville

fractional integrals to establish a number of Ostrowski-type inequalities for functions belonging to different Lebesgue norm spaces, including those of bounded variation, Hölder continuous, Lipschitz, and absolutely continuous functions. Hermite-Hadamard inequality and Ostrowski inequality for fractional integrals of two variable functions are obtained in [13] and [19], respectively. Recently, Erden et al. [8] provided some Ostrowski type inequalities including Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals for functions in class of functions L_p, L_∞ and L_1 , respectively. Also, Erden et al. [9] established new double fractional inequalities of Ostrowski type for functions of bounded variation with two variables.

In addition to these foundational works, a wide range of research has focused on inequalities concerning functions that are convex on the coordinates or that involve Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals. For several recent results concerning Hermite-Hadamard's inequality for some convex function on the co-ordinates on a rectangle from the plane R^2 , we refer the reader to ([7], [10], [14], [17], [18], [21]-[25]). There are also several papers on fractional Ostrowski type inequalities for one or two variable functions, you can find some of them in the references ([1], [6], [9], [12], [15], [20], [26]).

In the introduction, we review the fundamental definitions of the fractional integral operators under consideration, along with the notion of coordinated convexity, which form the basis of our analysis. The structure of the paper is as follows: Section 2 presents our main results. By applying a key fractional integral identity established in a previous work [8], we derive several new Ostrowski type inequalities including the definitions of Riemann-Liouville fractional integral for co-ordinated convex functions. In addition, a midpoint-type formulation of the main result is presented as a corollary.

2. Double Integral Inequalities Involving Riemann-Liouville Fractional Integrals

The identity to be used in constructing this section is given below. This identity, which was previously employed by Erdem et al. in [8], will be utilized here to derive integral inequalities for co-ordinated convex functions.

Lemma 1.[8] Let $f : \Delta =: [a, b] \times [c, d] \rightarrow R$ be an absolutely continuous function such that the partial derivative of order 2 exists and is continuous on Δ in R^2 . Then, for any $(x, y) \in \Delta$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)\Gamma(\beta)} \int_a^b \int_c^d \Omega(t, s) \left[\int_x^t \int_y^s \frac{\partial^2 f(\zeta, \tau)}{\partial \zeta \partial \tau} d\tau d\zeta \right] ds dt \\ & = J_{x^+, y^+}^{\alpha, \beta} f(b, d) + J_{x^+, y^-}^{\alpha, \beta} f(b, c) + J_{x^-, y^+}^{\alpha, \beta} f(a, d) + J_{x^-, y^-}^{\alpha, \beta} f(a, c) \\ & \quad - \frac{(y-c)^\beta + (d-y)^\beta}{\Gamma(\beta+1)} [J_{x^+}^\alpha f(b, y) + J_{x^-}^\alpha f(a, y)] \\ & \quad - \frac{(x-a)^\alpha + (b-x)^\alpha}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} [J_{y^+}^\beta f(x, d) + J_{y^-}^\beta f(x, c)] \\ & \quad + \frac{(x-a)^\alpha + (b-x)^\alpha}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} \frac{(y-c)^\beta + (d-y)^\beta}{\Gamma(\beta+1)} f(x, y) \\ & =: G_2(x, y; a, b, c, d) \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

where $\Omega(t, s)$ is defined by

$$\Omega(t, s) := \begin{cases} (t-a)^{\alpha-1}(s-c)^{\beta-1}, & a \leq t < x \text{ and } c \leq s < y \\ (t-a)^{\alpha-1}(d-s)^{\beta-1}, & a \leq t < x \text{ and } y \leq s \leq d \\ (b-t)^{\alpha-1}(s-c)^{\beta-1}, & x \leq t \leq b \text{ and } c \leq s < y \\ (b-t)^{\alpha-1}(d-s)^{\beta-1}, & x \leq t \leq b \text{ and } y \leq s \leq d. \end{cases}$$

By employing the above identity, we derive several double integral inequalities in the framework of Riemann-Liouville fractional operators for functions whose powers are convex on the coordinates.

Theorem 1. Let $f: \Delta \rightarrow R$ be an absolutely continuous function such that the partial derivative of order 2 exists and is continuous for all $(t, s) \in \Delta$ in R^2 . If $\left| \frac{\partial^2 f(\zeta, \tau)}{\partial \zeta \partial \tau} \right|^q$ is a co-ordinated convex function on Δ for $p, q > 1$ with $\frac{1}{p} + \frac{1}{q} = 1$, then we have the Riemann-Liouville fractional inequality

$$\begin{aligned} & |G_2(x, y; a, b, c, d)| \tag{2} \\ & \leq \frac{\Gamma\left(1 + \frac{1}{p}\right)\Gamma\left(1 + \frac{1}{p}\right)}{4^{\frac{1}{q}}\Gamma\left(\alpha + 1 + \frac{1}{p}\right)\Gamma\left(\beta + 1 + \frac{1}{p}\right)} \\ & \times \left\{ (x-a)^{\alpha+1}(y-c)^{\beta+1} \left[|f_{\zeta\tau}(a, c)|^q + |f_{\zeta\tau}(a, y)|^q + |f_{\zeta\tau}(x, c)|^q + |f_{\zeta\tau}(x, y)|^q \right]^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \\ & + (x-a)^{\alpha+1}(d-y)^{\beta+1} \left[|f_{\zeta\tau}(a, y)|^q + |f_{\zeta\tau}(a, d)|^q + |f_{\zeta\tau}(x, y)|^q + |f_{\zeta\tau}(x, d)|^q \right]^{\frac{1}{q}} \\ & + (b-x)^{\alpha+1}(y-c)^{\beta+1} \left[|f_{\zeta\tau}(x, c)|^q + |f_{\zeta\tau}(x, y)|^q + |f_{\zeta\tau}(b, c)|^q + |f_{\zeta\tau}(b, y)|^q \right]^{\frac{1}{q}} \\ & \left. + (b-x)^{\alpha+1}(d-y)^{\beta+1} \left[|f_{\zeta\tau}(x, y)|^q + |f_{\zeta\tau}(x, d)|^q + |f_{\zeta\tau}(b, y)|^q + |f_{\zeta\tau}(b, d)|^q \right]^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} \end{aligned}$$

for all $(x, y) \in \Delta$ and $\alpha, \beta > 0$.

Proof. Taking absolute value of both sides of the equality (1), because of the definition of $\Omega(t, s)$, it follows that

$$\begin{aligned} & |G_2(x, y; a, b, c, d)| \tag{3} \\ & \leq \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)\Gamma(\beta)} \int_a^x \int_c^y (t-a)^{\alpha-1}(s-c)^{\beta-1} \left| \int_x^t \int_y^s \frac{\partial^2 f(\zeta, \tau)}{\partial \zeta \partial \tau} d\tau d\zeta \right| ds dt \\ & + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)\Gamma(\beta)} \int_a^x \int_y^d (t-a)^{\alpha-1}(d-s)^{\beta-1} \left| \int_x^t \int_y^s \frac{\partial^2 f(\zeta, \tau)}{\partial \zeta \partial \tau} d\tau d\zeta \right| ds dt \\ & + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)\Gamma(\beta)} \int_x^b \int_c^y (b-t)^{\alpha-1}(s-c)^{\beta-1} \left| \int_x^t \int_y^s \frac{\partial^2 f(\zeta, \tau)}{\partial \zeta \partial \tau} d\tau d\zeta \right| ds dt \\ & + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)\Gamma(\beta)} \int_x^b \int_y^d (b-t)^{\alpha-1}(d-s)^{\beta-1} \left| \int_x^t \int_y^s \frac{\partial^2 f(\zeta, \tau)}{\partial \zeta \partial \tau} d\tau d\zeta \right| ds dt. \end{aligned}$$

Since $|f_{ts}(t, s)|^q$ is a convex function on the co-ordinates on $(\zeta, \tau) \in [a, x] \times [c, y]$, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
& \left| f_{\zeta\tau} \left(\frac{x-\zeta}{x-a} a + \frac{\zeta-a}{x-a} x, \frac{y-\tau}{y-c} c + \frac{\tau-c}{y-c} y \right) \right|^q \\
& \leq \frac{(x-\zeta)(y-\tau)}{(x-a)(y-c)} |f_{\zeta\tau}(a, c)|^q + \frac{(x-\zeta)(\tau-c)}{(x-a)(y-c)} |f_{\zeta\tau}(a, y)|^q \\
& + \frac{(\zeta-a)(y-\tau)}{(x-a)(y-c)} |f_{\zeta\tau}(x, c)|^q + \frac{(\zeta-a)(\tau-c)}{(x-a)(y-c)} |f_{\zeta\tau}(x, y)|^q.
\end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

By employing the above inequality (4), which was obtained for a function whose absolute value of the partial derivatives is convex on the coordinates, together with the use of Hölder's inequality, it is clear that

$$\begin{aligned}
& \left| \int_x^t \int_y^s \frac{\partial^2 f(\zeta, \tau)}{\partial \zeta \partial \tau} d\tau d\zeta \right| \leq \int_x^t \int_y^s \left| \frac{\partial^2 f(\zeta, \tau)}{\partial \zeta \partial \tau} \right| d\tau d\zeta \\
& \leq \left(\int_t^x \int_s^y d\tau d\zeta \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \left(\int_x^t \int_y^s \left| \frac{\partial^2 f(\zeta, \tau)}{\partial \zeta \partial \tau} \right|^q d\tau d\zeta \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \\
& \leq (x-t)^{\frac{1}{p}} (y-s)^{\frac{1}{p}} \left(\int_a^x \int_c^y \left| \frac{\partial^2 f(\zeta, \tau)}{\partial \zeta \partial \tau} \right|^q d\tau d\zeta \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \\
& \leq (x-t)^{\frac{1}{p}} (y-s)^{\frac{1}{p}} \left(\frac{(x-a)(y-c)}{4} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \\
& \times \left[|f_{\zeta\tau}(a, c)|^q + |f_{\zeta\tau}(a, y)|^q + |f_{\zeta\tau}(x, c)|^q + |f_{\zeta\tau}(x, y)|^q \right]^{\frac{1}{q}}.
\end{aligned}$$

Then, it is clear that

$$\begin{aligned}
& \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)\Gamma(\beta)} \int_a^x \int_c^y (t-a)^{\alpha-1} (s-c)^{\beta-1} \left| \int_x^t \int_y^s \frac{\partial^2 f(\zeta, \tau)}{\partial \zeta \partial \tau} d\tau d\zeta \right| ds dt \\
& \leq \frac{\left[|f_{\zeta\tau}(a, c)|^q + |f_{\zeta\tau}(a, y)|^q + |f_{\zeta\tau}(x, c)|^q + |f_{\zeta\tau}(x, y)|^q \right]^{\frac{1}{q}}}{\Gamma(\alpha)\Gamma(\beta)} \\
& \times \left(\frac{(x-a)(y-c)}{4} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \int_a^x \int_c^y (t-a)^{\alpha-1} (s-c)^{\beta-1} (x-t)^{\frac{1}{p}} (y-s)^{\frac{1}{p}} ds dt \\
& = \frac{\left[|f_{\zeta\tau}(a, c)|^q + |f_{\zeta\tau}(a, y)|^q + |f_{\zeta\tau}(x, c)|^q + |f_{\zeta\tau}(x, y)|^q \right]^{\frac{1}{q}}}{\Gamma(\alpha)\Gamma(\beta)} \left(\frac{(x-a)(y-c)}{4} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \\
& \times \int_a^x (t-a)^{\alpha-1} (x-t)^{\frac{1}{p}} dt \int_c^y (s-c)^{\beta-1} (y-s)^{\frac{1}{p}} ds
\end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

To complete the proof, we must calculate two integrals in the right side of the result (5). Applying the change of the variable $\frac{t-a}{x-a} = u$ and $dt = (x-a)du$ for the first integral, it is found that

$$\begin{aligned}
& \int_a^x (t-a)^{\alpha-1} (x-t)^{\frac{1}{p}} dt \\
& = \int_a^x (t-a)^{\alpha-1} (x-a - (t-a))^{\frac{1}{p}} dt \\
& = (x-a)^{\alpha+\frac{1}{p}} \int_0^1 u^{\alpha-1} (1-u)^{\frac{1}{p}} du
\end{aligned}$$

$$= (x - a)^{\alpha + \frac{1}{p}} B\left(\alpha, 1 + \frac{1}{p}\right).$$

And similarly, we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_c^y (s - c)^{\beta - 1} (y - s)^{\frac{1}{p}} ds \\ &= (y - c)^{\beta + \frac{1}{p}} B\left(\beta, 1 + \frac{1}{p}\right) \end{aligned}$$

Then, we possess

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)\Gamma(\beta)} \int_a^x \int_c^y (t - a)^{\alpha - 1} (s - c)^{\beta - 1} \left| \int_x^t \int_y^s \frac{\partial^2 f(\zeta, \tau)}{\partial \zeta \partial \tau} d\tau d\zeta \right| ds dt \\ & \leq \frac{(x - a)^{\alpha + \frac{1}{p}} (y - c)^{\beta + \frac{1}{p}} B\left(\alpha, 1 + \frac{1}{p}\right) B\left(\beta, 1 + \frac{1}{p}\right) \left(\frac{(x - a)(y - c)}{4}\right)^{\frac{1}{q}}}{\Gamma(\alpha)\Gamma(\beta)} \\ & \times \left[|f_{\zeta\tau}(a, c)|^q + |f_{\zeta\tau}(a, y)|^q + |f_{\zeta\tau}(x, c)|^q + |f_{\zeta\tau}(x, y)|^q \right]^{\frac{1}{q}} \\ & = \frac{\Gamma\left(1 + \frac{1}{p}\right)\Gamma\left(1 + \frac{1}{p}\right)}{4^{\frac{1}{q}}\Gamma\left(\alpha + 1 + \frac{1}{p}\right)\Gamma\left(\beta + 1 + \frac{1}{p}\right)} (x - a)^{\alpha + 1} (y - c)^{\beta + 1} \\ & \times \left[|f_{\zeta\tau}(a, c)|^q + |f_{\zeta\tau}(a, y)|^q + |f_{\zeta\tau}(x, c)|^q + |f_{\zeta\tau}(x, y)|^q \right]^{\frac{1}{q}} \end{aligned}$$

Similarly, applying the change of the variable $\frac{b-t}{b-x} = v$ and $dt = (x - b)dv$ for calculating the other integrals in the right hand side of the inequality (3), it is found that

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_x^b (b - t)^{\alpha - 1} (t - x)^{\frac{1}{p}} dt \\ &= \int_x^b (b - t)^{\alpha - 1} (b - x - (b - t))^{\frac{1}{p}} dt \\ &= (b - x)^{\alpha + \frac{1}{p}} B\left(\alpha, 1 + \frac{1}{p}\right). \end{aligned}$$

,and one has

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_y^d (d - s)^{\beta - 1} (s - y)^{\frac{1}{p}} ds \\ &= (d - y)^{\beta + \frac{1}{p}} B\left(\beta, 1 + \frac{1}{p}\right) \end{aligned}$$

Then, since $|f_{ts}(t, s)|^q$ is a convex function on the co-ordinates on $(\zeta, \tau) \in [a, x] \times [y, d]$, one has

$$\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)\Gamma(\beta)} \int_a^x \int_y^d (x - t)^{\alpha - 1} (s - y)^{\beta - 1} \left| \int_x^t \int_y^s \frac{\partial^2 f(\zeta, \tau)}{\partial \zeta \partial \tau} d\tau d\zeta \right| ds dt$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\leq \frac{\Gamma\left(1 + \frac{1}{p}\right)\Gamma\left(1 + \frac{1}{p}\right)}{4^{\frac{1}{q}}\Gamma\left(\alpha + 1 + \frac{1}{p}\right)\Gamma\left(\beta + 1 + \frac{1}{p}\right)}(x - a)^{\alpha+1}(d - y)^{\beta+1} \\ &\times \left[|f_{\zeta\tau}(a, y)|^q + |f_{\zeta\tau}(a, d)|^q + |f_{\zeta\tau}(x, y)|^q + |f_{\zeta\tau}(x, d)|^q\right]^{\frac{1}{q}} \end{aligned}$$

Since $|f_{ts}(t, s)|^q$ is a convex function on the co-ordinates on $(\zeta, \tau) \in [x, b] \times [c, y]$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} &\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)\Gamma(\beta)} \int_x^b \int_c^y (t - x)^{\alpha-1}(y - s)^{\beta-1} \left| \int_x^t \int_y^s \frac{\partial^2 f(\zeta, \tau)}{\partial \zeta \partial \tau} d\tau d\zeta \right| ds dt \\ &\leq \frac{\Gamma\left(1 + \frac{1}{p}\right)\Gamma\left(1 + \frac{1}{p}\right)}{4^{\frac{1}{q}}\Gamma\left(\alpha + 1 + \frac{1}{p}\right)\Gamma\left(\beta + 1 + \frac{1}{p}\right)}(b - x)^{\alpha+1}(y - c)^{\beta+1} \\ &\times \left[|f_{\zeta\tau}(x, c)|^q + |f_{\zeta\tau}(x, y)|^q + |f_{\zeta\tau}(b, c)|^q + |f_{\zeta\tau}(b, y)|^q\right]^{\frac{1}{q}}, \end{aligned}$$

and since $|f_{ts}(t, s)|^q$ is a convex function on the co-ordinates on $(\zeta, \tau) \in [x, b] \times [y, d]$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} &\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)\Gamma(\beta)} \int_x^b \int_y^d (t - x)^{\alpha-1}(s - y)^{\beta-1} \left| \int_x^t \int_y^s \frac{\partial^2 f(\zeta, \tau)}{\partial \zeta \partial \tau} d\tau d\zeta \right| ds dt \\ &\leq \frac{\Gamma\left(1 + \frac{1}{p}\right)\Gamma\left(1 + \frac{1}{p}\right)}{4^{\frac{1}{q}}\Gamma\left(\alpha + 1 + \frac{1}{p}\right)\Gamma\left(\beta + 1 + \frac{1}{p}\right)}(b - x)^{\alpha+1}(d - y)^{\beta+1} \\ &\times \left[|f_{\zeta\tau}(x, y)|^q + |f_{\zeta\tau}(x, d)|^q + |f_{\zeta\tau}(b, y)|^q + |f_{\zeta\tau}(b, d)|^q\right]^{\frac{1}{q}}. \end{aligned}$$

If the above four results are substituted in right hand side of (3) inequality, the desired inequality (2) can be attained.

Corollary 1. If we choose $x = \frac{a+b}{2}$ and $y = \frac{c+d}{2}$ in (3), then we have the Midpoint type inequality

$$\begin{aligned} &\left| J_{\frac{a+b}{2}^+, \frac{c+d}{2}^+}^{\alpha, \beta} f(b, d) + J_{\frac{a+b}{2}^+, \frac{c+d}{2}^-}^{\alpha, \beta} f(b, c) + J_{\frac{a+b}{2}^-, \frac{c+d}{2}^+}^{\alpha, \beta} f(a, d) + J_{\frac{a+b}{2}^-, \frac{c+d}{2}^-}^{\alpha, \beta} f(a, c) \right. \\ &- \frac{(d - c)^\beta}{2^{\beta-1}\Gamma(\beta + 1)} \left[J_{\frac{a+b}{2}^+}^\alpha f\left(b, \frac{c+d}{2}\right) + J_{\frac{a+b}{2}^-}^\alpha f\left(a, \frac{c+d}{2}\right) \right] \\ &- \frac{(b - a)^\alpha}{2^{\alpha-1}\Gamma(\alpha + 1)} \left[J_{\frac{c+d}{2}^+}^\beta f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}, d\right) + J_{\frac{c+d}{2}^-}^\beta f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}, c\right) \right] \\ &+ \frac{(b - a)^\alpha (d - c)^\beta}{2^{\alpha+\beta-2}\Gamma(\alpha + 1)\Gamma(\beta + 1)} f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}, \frac{c+d}{2}\right) \Big| \\ &\leq \frac{(b - a)^{\alpha+1}(d - c)^{\beta+1}\Gamma\left(1 + \frac{1}{p}\right)\Gamma\left(1 + \frac{1}{p}\right)}{2^{\alpha+\beta+2+\frac{2}{q}}\Gamma\left(\alpha + 1 + \frac{1}{p}\right)\Gamma\left(\beta + 1 + \frac{1}{p}\right)} \\ &\times \left\{ \left[|f_{\zeta\tau}(a, c)|^q + |f_{\zeta\tau}(a, y)|^q + |f_{\zeta\tau}(x, c)|^q + |f_{\zeta\tau}(x, y)|^q\right]^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \\ &\left. + \left[|f_{\zeta\tau}(a, y)|^q + |f_{\zeta\tau}(a, d)|^q + |f_{\zeta\tau}(x, y)|^q + |f_{\zeta\tau}(x, d)|^q\right]^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} \end{aligned}$$

$$+ \left[|f_{\zeta\tau}(x, c)|^q + |f_{\zeta\tau}(x, y)|^q + |f_{\zeta\tau}(b, c)|^q + |f_{\zeta\tau}(b, y)|^q \right]^{\frac{1}{q}} \\ + \left[|f_{\zeta\tau}(x, y)|^q + |f_{\zeta\tau}(x, d)|^q + |f_{\zeta\tau}(b, y)|^q + |f_{\zeta\tau}(b, d)|^q \right]^{\frac{1}{q}} \Big\}$$

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